

Buckling of Tapered Curved Composite Plates

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SUMMARY

The Ritz method and eight classical shell theories are used for the global linear buckling analysis of internally-tapered curved composite laminates subjected to uniaxial compressive load. The critical sizes of the plates that will not fail in first-ply failure mode before buckling are determined. A parametric study is carried out.

Keywords: Ritz method, linear buckling analysis, tapered curved laminates, first-ply failure.

INTRODUCTION

Complex structures like robot arms, shovels, gun barrels and other taper-walled structures are frequently used. In the present work, the buckling response of cylindrical curved plates with longitudinal-internal-ply-drop-off is investigated. According to the work of He et al [1], this type of taper is used to change the stress state at the free edge in order to suppress the delamination caused by stress-free edge effects. Daoust and Hoa [2] have concluded that internal drop-off laminates are roughly 2 times stronger than external drop-off laminates. Considering the previously mentioned studies, different types of longitudinal cross-sections as shown in Fig. 1 are investigated.

Figure 1: Different sections of curved laminated plate.

The first objective of the present study is to conduct the linear global buckling analysis of various types of curved plates as shown in Fig. 1 using Ritz method. Tapered part of configuration D is made of either configuration B or C. For the buckling analysis based on classical shell theory, eight shell theories (CST-1 to CST-8), namely Donnell, Love, Mushtari, Timoshenko, Vlasov, Sander, Koiter and Novozhilov theories are used. *The*

second objective is to find out the first-ply failure loads of the tapered curved plates using commercial software ANSYS[®]. *The third objective* is to determine the critical geometric parameters and structural configurations of the tapered curved plates that correspond to different types of failures. A parametric study that encompasses the effects of boundary conditions, stacking sequence, taper configurations, radius, and geometric parameters of the plates is also conducted.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A review of recent developments in the analysis of tapered laminated composite structures has been presented by He et al [1] and two major categories of work on tapered composite plates have been identified. The first is to understand failure mechanisms encompassing the determination of the interlaminar stresses. The works of Curry et al [3] and Hoa et al [4] belong to this category. The second category encompasses the investigations of the parameters of the tapered composite structures that have substantial influences on the structural integrity. Parametric studies of tapered composites were conducted by Daoust and Hoa [2], Llanos and Vizzini [5], Thomas and Webber [6] and others.

Piskunov and Sipetov [7] have proposed a laminated tapered shell structure which accounts for the effects produced by transverse shearing strain. Another work on tapered shell structure was conducted by Kee and Kim [8], where the finite element method has been used for solving the governing equations.

One of the earliest works on anisotropic laminate is by Likhmitskii [9]. Ambartsumyan [10] pioneered the anisotropic thin shell analysis. Viswanathan et al [11] investigated elastic stability of laminated, flat and curved, long rectangular plates subjected to combined in-plane loads. Hilburger and Starnes [12] have worked on buckling behavior of compression-loaded composite cylindrical shells with reinforced cutouts. Nemeth and Smeltzer [13] have calculated the bending boundary layers in laminated composite circular cylindrical shells. Michael [14] has presented non-dimensional parameters and equations for buckling of symmetrically laminated thin elastic shallow shells.

Studies related to the shear post-buckling response of laminated plates can be found in the work of Kaminski and Ashton [15] who presented an experimental study on rectangular boron/epoxy plates clamped on each edge. Lee [16] has performed a three-dimensional finite element progressive failure analysis using his own failure criterion to predict the failures. Reddy and Pandey [17] developed a finite element procedure based on first-order, shear-deformation theory for first-ply failure analysis of laminated composite plates subjected to in-plane and/or transverse loads. Failure analysis of laminated shell based on first-ply failure method was carried out by Prusty et al [18].

The World-Wide Failure Exercise (WWFE) contained a detailed assessment [19] of 19 theoretical approaches for predicting the deformation and failure response of polymer composite laminates subjected to complex states of stress. The leading five theories (Zinoviev, Bogetti, Puck, Cuntze and Tsai) are explored in greater detail. According to the investigations of WWFE, Tsai-Wu theory is the best one to predict the first-ply failure of unidirectional laminates and any of the above mentioned five theories can be used for multidirectional laminates.

Ganesan and Akhlaque [20] considered the buckling analysis of tapered plates using Ritz method.

LINEAR BUCKLING ANALYSIS BASED ON CLASSICAL SHELL THEORY

Formulation

The strain-displacement relations according to different theories are written for the case of small deformations of a cylindrical shell of radius R , length L_{tap} and thickness h_{tk} . The displacement fields $\{u_o, v_o, w_o\}$ refer to the coordinate system $\{x, y, z\}$ as shown in Fig. 1. Resin pockets are considered as the combination of hypothetical resin plies. The tracer coefficients C_1, C_2, C_3 and C_4 are introduced to accommodate the eight different shell theories (called as CST-1 to CST-8) for shallow curved plates.

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{e}_{xx}^o \\ \mathbf{e}_{yy}^o \\ \mathbf{g}_{xy}^o \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \frac{\partial u_o}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial v_o}{\partial y} + \frac{w_o}{R} \\ \frac{\partial u_o}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_o}{\partial x} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{k}_{xx}^o \\ \mathbf{k}_{yy}^o \\ \mathbf{k}_{xy}^o \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} -\frac{\partial^2 w_o}{\partial x^2} \\ -\frac{\partial^2 w_o}{\partial y^2} - \frac{C_1}{R^2} w_o + \frac{C_2}{R} \frac{\partial v_o}{\partial y} \\ -2\frac{\partial^2 w_o}{\partial x \partial y} + \frac{1}{R} \left(C_3 \frac{\partial v_o}{\partial x} - C_4 \frac{\partial u_o}{\partial y} \right) \end{Bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where $\{\mathbf{e}_{xx}^o, \mathbf{e}_{yy}^o, \mathbf{g}_{xy}^o\}$ and $\{\mathbf{k}_{xx}^o, \mathbf{k}_{yy}^o, \mathbf{k}_{xy}^o\}$ denote the mid-surface strains and curvatures respectively.

When (i) $C_1 = C_2 = C_3 = C_4 = 0$, equations that correspond to Donnel's, Mushtari's, Timoshenko's and Love's shell theories [21-24] are obtained; (ii) $C_1 = C_3 = C_4 = 1$ and $C_2 = 0$, equations that correspond to Vlasov's shell theory [25] are obtained; (iii) $C_1 = C_2 = 0$ and $C_3 = C_4 = 1/2$, equations that correspond to Sander's and Koiter's shell theories [26-27] are obtained; and (iv) $C_1 = C_4 = 0, C_2 = 1$ and $C_3 = 2$, equations that correspond to Novozhilov's shell theory [28] are obtained.

The strain energy of an elastic solid is written in Cartesian co-ordinates as follows:

$$\Pi = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^b \int_0^{L_{tap}} \left\{ [\mathbf{e}]^T \begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ B & D \end{bmatrix} [\mathbf{e}] \right\} dx dy \quad \text{where, } [\mathbf{e}] = [\mathbf{e}_{xx}^o, \mathbf{e}_{yy}^o, \mathbf{g}_{xy}^o, \mathbf{k}_{xx}^o, \mathbf{k}_{yy}^o, \mathbf{k}_{xy}^o] \quad (3)$$

$[A], [B]$ and $[D]$ are calculated for tapered laminate and $[\mathbf{e}]$ is the strain matrix that is written based on different shell theories. The potential energy due to the uniaxial load is [29]:

$$F = -I \int_0^b \int_0^{L_{tap}} \left\{ \frac{\partial u_o}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{\partial v_o}{\partial x} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial w_o}{\partial x} \right)^2 \right] \right\} dx dy \quad (4)$$

where, I is the in-plane normal load in x-direction. Considering approximate displacements as a double series and applying the stationary conditions, the equilibrium conditions can be written in the form:

$$[K] + \bar{I}[Z] = 0 \quad (5)$$

where, $[K]$ and $[Z]$ are the stiffness matrix and geometric stiffness matrix respectively.

Verification

To compare the present buckling analysis results with the results presented in the literature, it is necessary to consider that the taper angle j is equal to zero for uniform-

thickness cylindrical plates. The uniform-thickness laminate is classified as configuration A.

Example 1: Uniform-thickness cylindrical panel made of Morganite II/4617 having the mechanical properties of $E_x = 20.0 \times 10^6$ psi, $E_y = 2.1 \times 10^6$ psi, $G_{x'y'} = 0.85 \times 10^6$ psi, $\nu_{x'y'} = 0.21$ and the geometrical properties of length $L_{tap} = 12$ inches, width $b = 8$ inches, radius $R = (12 - h_{tk}/2)$ inches, and taper angle $f = 0$ degree has been investigated by Wilkins [30].

Table 1: The comparison of critical buckling loads for uniform-thickness cylindrical panel (12" x 8" x 0.0592") of different laminate configurations

Laminate configuration	Wilkins [30], lbs	Present, lbs
	Exp.	(C4-C4)
[0/45/90/-45] _s	7,100 (Mo)	7,301
[0/90] _{2s}	7,088 (S)	8,140
[0] _{6s}	21,538 (S)	24,972

In the work of Wilkins [30], buckling loads were calculated applying the experimental procedure of Moiré (Mo) and also using Southwell (S) curve. Results of the present work are compared with that of the results of experimental work for different laminate configurations in the Table 1. It has been observed that the present results have concurrence with that of Ref. [30]. Next, a tapered curved plate that has one ply drop-off (DOP-1) is analyzed applying Donnell's and Novozhilov's theories and using the material and geometric properties given in Example 1 and the results are given in Table 2.

Table 2: The comparisons of critical buckling loads of uniform-thickness curved panel and tapered panel DOP-1

Laminate configuration	Wilkins [30], lbs	Present, lbs		
	Exp.	Uniform panel (Donnell)	Tapered panel DOP-1 (Donnell)	Tapered panel DOP-1 (Novozhilov)
[0] _{6s}	21 538 (S)	24 972	23,947	23,918

As can be observed from Table 2, the buckling load for curved laminate decreases when a ply is dropped-off.

Assessment of Various Shell Theories

Critical buckling loads of uniform-thickness curved plates using the material and geometric properties given in Example 1 are calculated applying different shell theories and the results are compared in Table 3.

Table 3: The comparison of critical buckling loads of uniform-thickness curved plates based on different shell theories

Laminate configuration	Wilkins [30], lbs	Present, lbs			
	Exp.	Donnell, Love Mushtari, Timoshenko	Vlasov	Sander, Koiter	Novozhilov
[0/90] _{2s}	7,088 (S)	8,140	8,122	8,138	8,120

It is noted that Novozhilov's theory gives the lower bound results (that are closer to the experimental data) for both tapered and uniform-thickness plates.

FIRST-PLY FAILURE ANALYSIS USING ANSYS®

SHELL99 is used to investigate the strength of the tapered plates that will not fail before global buckling. SHELL99 is an 8-node, 3-D shell element with six degrees of freedom at each node. It is designed to model thin to moderately-thick plate and shell structures with a side-to-thickness ratio of roughly 10 or greater. The 3-D version of Tsai-Wu failure criterion is used as the failure criterion for both lamina failure and resin failure (Tsai and Hahn [31]). The values of the strength properties X^t , X^c , Y^t , Y^c , Z^t , Z^c , R_{yz} , S_{xz} , and T_{xy} are given in Table 4 and Table 5. X^t , Y^t , Z^t are the normal tensile strengths in the principal material directions respectively; X^c , Y^c , Z^c are the normal compressive strengths in the principal material directions respectively; and R_{yz} , S_{xz} , T_{xy} are the shear strengths in the $y-z$, $x-z$, $x-y$ planes respectively.

Table 4: Material properties of epoxy used in NCT/301

Mechanical property	Value	Strength property	Value*
$E_x^m = E_y^m = E_z^m$	3.930 GPa	$X^t = Y^t = Z^t$	57.00 MPa
$G_{x^m y^m} = G_{x^m z^m} = G_{y^m z^m}$	1.034 GPa	$X^c = Y^c = Z^c$	-104 MPa
$\nu_{x^m y^m} = \nu_{x^m z^m} = \nu_{y^m z^m}$	0.370	$R_{yz} = S_{xz} = T_{xy}$	22 MPa

Table 5: Material properties of NCT/301 graphite-epoxy composite material

Mechanical property	Value	Strength property	Value*
E_x^m	113.900 GPa	X^t	1621 MPa
$E_y^m = E_z^m$	7.985 GPa	X^c	-1250 MPa
$G_{x^m y^m} = G_{x^m z^m}$	3.137 GPa	$Y^t = Z^t$	48.28 MPa
$G_{y^m z^m}$	2.852 GPa	$Y^c = Z^c$	-200 MPa
$\nu_{x^m y^m} = \nu_{x^m z^m}$	0.288	R_{yz}	25.00 MPa
$\nu_{y^m z^m}$	0.400	$S_{xz} = T_{xy}$	33.30 MPa

* Material properties are collected from the manufacturer's website.

The first-ply failure refers to the first instant at which any layer or more than one layer fails at the same load. The first-ply failure analysis of tapered curved plate of configuration C is carried out based on the data of Example 2.

Example 2: Taper configurations shown in the Fig. 1 are considered with 36 and 12 plies at thick and thin sections respectively, which results in 24 drop-off plies. The configuration at the thick end is $(0/90)_{9s}$, and that of the thin end is $(0/90)_{3s}$. The mechanical properties of the composite material (NCT/301 graphite-epoxy) and resin are given in Tables 4 and 5 respectively. Thickness of each ply, the height of thick end and the radius of curved plate are 0.125 mm, 4.5 mm and 500 mm respectively.

The first-ply failure loads calculated using ANSYS® and the buckling loads calculated based on CST-8 are compared in the Fig. 2. It is observed from the Fig. 2 that the maximum plate size should be corresponding to taper angle of 1 degree. Shorter sized plate ($< 0.0859 \times 0.0859 \text{ m}^2$) will fail by first-ply failure before buckling.

Fig. 2: Comparison of first-ply failure loads and critical buckling loads for tapered curved laminates.

PARAMETRIC STUDY

The tapered curved plates are analyzed using Ritz method based on Novozhilov's classical shell theory. The effects of boundary conditions, stacking sequence, taper configurations, radius, and geometric parameters of the plates are investigated using the properties of the following example.

Buckling Analysis of Various Types of Plates

Influence of Drop-off Plies

The effect of ply drop-off on buckling is shown in the Fig. 3. To investigate this effect, the size of the plate (859.4 mm x 859.4 mm) and the thickness of the thick end are not changed and the taper angle is varied with the corresponding increase in the number of drop-off plies. The plate can be considered as a uniform-thickness plate when the number of ply drop-off is set to zero and the configuration B is obtained by dropping off twenty four plies.

Fig. 3: The effect of ply drop-off on buckling loads for clamped plates using CST-8.

From the Fig. 3, it is observed that the uniform-thickness curved plate is stiffer than the uniform-thickness flat plate in terms of buckling behavior. It is also observed that the tapered flat plate is less stiff than uniform flat, but this behavior of the plate can be inverted if the tapered flat plate is made into a curved one. It can be concluded from the Fig. 3 that the tapered flat plate is more flexible than uniform flat plate, but the tapered curved plate provides a better option in terms of saving the material without any compromise of strength.

Influence of Taper Angle

The effect of taper angle is shown in the Fig. 4 where the size of the plate is decreased with the increase of taper angle while keeping the thickness of thick section unchanged. The maximum and minimum sizes of the plates are (859.4 mm × 859.4 mm) and (85.94 mm × 85.94 mm) respectively.

Fig. 4: Effect of taper angle on buckling loads for clamped tapered flat and tapered curved laminates based on CST-8.

As can be observed, the critical buckling load increases as the taper angle is increased and the tapered curved plates are stiffer than the tapered flat plate. For both of the configurations B and C, the critical buckling load increases with the increase of taper angle, and the configuration C is stronger than the configuration B.

Influence of Length to Height Ratio

The Fig. 5 shows the normalized buckling load versus length to height ratio. The minimum and maximum sizes of the plates are (85.94 mm × 85.94 mm) and (171.4 mm × 171.9 mm) respectively.

It is observed from the Fig. 5, the normalized buckling load increases with the increase of length to height ratio of the plate. With the increase of length to height ratio, the rate of change of critical buckling load of tapered curved plate is greater than that of tapered flat plate.

Fig. 5: Buckling loads for tapered flat and tapered curved laminates.

The Influence of Radius Value

Laminates with only tapered cross sections have been studied in the previous sections and the combined (tapered and uniform-thickness) section which is classified as configuration D is taken into account in the present section. The tapered part of configuration D is modeled using the configuration C. Three types of lay-up configurations namely LC_1 , LC_2 and LC_3 are considered. The width of the plates is 0.1146 m and the lengths are given in the Table 6. For the buckling analysis, a taper angle of 0.75 degrees and the material properties of Example 2 are considered and the results are given in the Figs. 6-8.

Table 6: List of lay-up configurations

Lay-up configuration	Ply stacking sequence			Length of the plate		
	Thick section	Tapered section	Thin section	Thick section	Tapered section	Thin section
LC_1	$[0/90]_{9s}$	Config. C	$[0/90]_{3s}$	0.0382	0.1146	0.0382
LC_2	$[\pm 45]_{9s}$	Config. C	$[\pm 45]_{3s}$	0.0382	0.1146	0.0382
LC_3	$[0_2/\pm 45_8]_s$	Config. C	$[0_2/\pm 45_2]_s$	0.0382	0.1146	0.0382

Influence of Lay-up Configurations

The critical buckling loads of three lay-up configurations are calculated using ANSYS® and Ritz method and also compared in the Figs. 6-8 for different boundary conditions.

Fig. 6: Variation of buckling loads with the change of radius of the clamped-clamped laminates with taper configuration D for different lay-up configurations.

Fig. 7: Variation of buckling loads with the change of radius of the clamped-clamped laminates with taper configuration D for different lay-up configurations.

Fig. 8: Variation of buckling loads with the change of radius of the simply supported laminates with taper configuration D for different lay-up configurations.

From Figs. 6-8, the following observations are made.

- (a) The lay-up configuration LC₂ is the weakest one among all lay-up configurations.
- (b) The rate of change of critical buckling load of lay-up LC₃ is lesser than that of lay-up configuration LC₁. Due to this type of characteristic, the critical buckling load of LC₁ is higher than that of LC₃ for the smaller radius. In case of larger radius, LC₃ is stronger than LC₁.
- (c) In all cases, the critical buckling loads decrease with the increase of radius.

CONCLUSIONS

Tapered flat plates are more flexible than uniform flat plates. Tapered flat plates can be made stronger in terms of their resistance to buckling by constructing them into shallow curved ones. The taper configuration C is stronger than the taper configuration B. Tapered curved/flat plates become stiffer with the increase of taper angle if the sizes of plates are decreased with the increase of taper angle and by keeping the same thickness at the thick section. Novozhilov's theory is identified as the most conservative classical shell theory compared to other seven classical shell theories. The tapered curved plate of radius 500 mm and configuration C that corresponds to the taper angle of 1 degree can fail by buckling without any first-ply failure. For all cases, the buckling loads decrease with the increase of radius.

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